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Towards an optical gas standard for ammonia measurements in air at ambient levels

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ABSTRACT

We describe thorough metrological characterization of a cavity ring-down spectrometer, combined with proprietary spectral evaluation algorithm. Our measurements show good linearity, good accuracy and short response time of the instrument in the 50–400 nmol/mol amount fraction range. Our spectral evaluation algorithm enables decreasing the offset to 0.12 nmol/mol from the values around 0.6–0.9 nmol/mol reported using the built-in data evaluation of the commercial spectrometer. We have successfully eliminated cross-sensitivity by water vapor via an advanced spectral fitting approach using line parameters published in the HITRAN2020 database. Our spectrometer has been compared to a traceable reference gas standard and the results show that it is a good candidate to become an optical gas standard for ammonia amount fraction measurements under laboratory conditions.

1. Introduction

Detrimental effects of atmospheric ammonia (NH₃) on biodiversity, ecosystems, air quality and human health have been known for a long time [1,2]. Its main emission source is agriculture, giving 93 % of all NH₃ emissions in the European Union [3]. Gaseous ammonia has a very short lifetime in the atmosphere, in the range of hours [4]. A large part of emitted NH₃ is deposited in the close vicinity of sources, or transformed into airborne aerosol particles, therefore its usual amount-of-substance fraction in ambient air is low, mostly below 100 nmol/mol even in agricultural landscapes, with 0–10 nmol/mol being the average background amount fraction in remote locations [5].

Various NH₃ measurement instruments have been developed in the past few decades, which are capable of accurate monitoring of such low amount fractions under field conditions. Wet-chemical techniques [6] are considered to be a traditional and highly reliable monitoring method. Chemiluminescence analyzers are also suitable for measuring NH₃ amount fraction, and being the reference method for NO_x

measurements, they are often used in air quality monitoring stations [7]. Additionally, several novel spectroscopic methods have been used more frequently during the past years [8]. The DOAS technique has been shown to be suitable for ambient NH₃ monitoring with open path measurement [6,9], while photoacoustic spectroscopy [10,11], direct absorption spectroscopy [12,13], cavity ring-down spectroscopy [14,15] and cavity-enhanced absorption spectroscopy [7,16] have been proved to be suitable for NH₃ detection with extractive measurement in the nmol/mol range. Laboratory [17] and field [8,18] inter-comparison experiments show that agreement between these instruments is not trivial. Deviations often clearly exceed the uncertainties, and might be as high as 50 % in case of low amount fractions (<10 nmol/mol) and under field conditions [18]. Therefore, regular careful calibration of monitoring instruments is inevitable to ensure comparability of the measured NH₃ amount fractions. Sampling issues are known to be a major challenge and the primary cause of discrepancies in environmental NH₃ monitoring, especially for instruments needing a filter at the inlet [8].

Traceable reference gas mixtures are only available for amount

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fractions of 10 $\mu\text{mol/mol}$ and above, as static gas mixtures of NH_3 in nitrogen or synthetic air, in cylinders. Worldwide 8 metrology institutes have calibration and measurement capabilities (CMC) for producing primary reference gas mixtures for NH_3 in nitrogen or synthetic air between 10 and 5000 $\mu\text{mol/mol}$. Expanded ($k = 2$) uncertainties range from 0.5 to 11 %, depending on the amount fraction level and the institute. To explore agreement between the reference materials produced by different metrology institutes, two key comparisons have been performed so far by the Consultative Committee for Amount of Substance: Metrology in Chemistry and Biology (CCQM): the first in 2006–2007 at the 30 $\mu\text{mol/mol}$ amount fraction level [19] and the second in 2018–2019 at the 15 $\mu\text{mol/mol}$ level [20]. The second comparison showed considerably better results: the results of five out of eight participating metrology institutes agreed with the comparison reference value. Stability of these gas mixtures was demonstrated for at least one year, which is sufficient for most practical applications. Gas mixtures by commercial providers usually have an uncertainty of around 5 % in the 10–100 $\mu\text{mol/mol}$ amount fraction range, and similar limitations due to stability. For calibration of instruments, these reference gas mixtures have to be diluted by a factor of 100–1000 to reach amount fractions relevant for ambient ammonia monitoring. The dilution process is not straightforward, flow controller devices need to be calibrated, as well as materials of the gas handling system must be carefully selected to minimize the effect of adsorption-desorption processes. Although gas cylinders are a long-established and reliable way of calibrating monitoring instruments, their size and the complexity of adding a dilution system to generate reference gas mixtures with NH_3 amount fractions in the nmol/mol range might hinder their practical applicability in certain cases.

As an alternative method, dynamic generators have been developed recently to provide a compact device for calibration purposes in the nmol/mol range. These devices are based on the permeation [21,22] or evaporation [23] method. Dynamic reference gas generators based on the permeation method use a permeation tube filled with pure NH_3 placed in a temperature-controlled oven [24]. A stable NH_3 amount fraction is achieved in the generated gas, if the temperature in the oven as well as the flow rate of the purging gas (e.g. zero air) are kept constant. Permeation rate of the permeation tube is determined by periodically weighing it on a microbalance. To achieve sufficiently low uncertainty, the permeation rates are kept relatively high, resulting in an NH_3 amount fraction in the $\mu\text{mol/mol}$ range in the generated gas. To generate reference gases with 0–400 nmol/mol NH_3 amount fraction, a two-step dilution system is added using calibrated MFCs. Two European metrology institutes have CMCs for NH_3 in nitrogen and synthetic air in the 2–400 nmol/mol range with expanded uncertainties ($k = 2$) of 1.1–2.1 % [22]. Reference gases of water-soluble compounds can also be generated by the evaporation method. In the case of NH_3 , liquid NH_4OH solution is added by a syringe pump to a constant flow of carrier gas (e.g. zero air). By adjusting the concentration of the NH_4OH solution and the liquid and gas flow rates, reference gases with a wide range of NH_3 amount fractions can be produced, including nmol/mol amount fractions without the need for further dilutions. However, the generated gas mixture will always contain humidity.

In the present publication we introduce a third potential method for calibration and validation of NH_3 monitoring instruments. An optical gas standard (OGS) is a spectrometer capable of absolute, SI-traceable amount fraction measurement, and can thereby be used for the calibration and validation of other instruments via comparison. The most widely known example for this is the ozone standard reference photometer [25], however, the technique is very promising for other reactive or adsorptive analytes as well, where the preparation and application of static gas mixtures is challenging. PTB has an optical gas standard for hydrogen chloride (HCl) measurements, and holds a CMC for HCl measurements using this OGS [26]. PTB has recently participated in a key comparison (CCQM-K175) for 30 $\mu\text{mol/mol}$ HCl in nitrogen, the results of which are expected to be published soon.

In this work we have used a commercial CRDS instrument from Picarro Inc. and developed a comprehensive spectral evaluation algorithm to process the spectra measured by the instrument. Thereafter we performed a thorough metrological characterization including calibration of the built-in temperature and pressure sensors of the instruments, examining zero reading, its response time, as well as cross-sensitivity to carbon dioxide and water vapor. A detailed uncertainty budget, as well as comparison to a commercial and a primary static gas standard, is also presented. The instrument is aimed to be operated as an OGS for NH_3 amount fraction measurements in air, under laboratory conditions.

2. Experimental

The Picarro G2103 analyzer (the older version of the currently available PI2103 analyzer, with similar specifications) is a cavity ring-down spectrometer operating in the near-infrared range around 1.53 μm . We found this spectrometer well-suited to convert it to an optical gas standard due to its compact and robust design, and reliable long-term operation proven during its use in various practical applications [22,27,28]. Another important feature is that the measured spectra are easily accessible by the user, and due to the operation principle, have a reliable and stable wavenumber axis determined by the cavity modes, which enables the development of an advanced spectral evaluation algorithm.

2.1. Gas handling system

An extensive gas handling set-up has been designed for the generation of gas mixtures for the laboratory characterization of the spectrometer, which is depicted in Fig. 1. This included a commercial gas mixture of 10 $\mu\text{mol/mol}$ NH_3 in synthetic air (Linde Gas), a cylinder of pure CO_2 (Linde Gas, 5.0 purity) and purified ambient air as a diluting gas. We used a two-pressure humidity generator (Thunder Scientific, Model 3900) to add moisture to the gas mixture and a calibrated dew-point mirror (MBW 373LHX) to monitor and validate the humidity level. The gas flow in each line was controlled by a mass flow controller (MKS 1179A) and combined. A three-way valve enabled prompt switching between the generated mixture and a stream of pure matrix gas. The flow rate in the gas handling lines was adjusted to be approximately 2 slm (standard liters per minute) after adding all components, and the spectrometer was sampling approximately 1.2 slm from this gas stream. We used PTFE tubing with 6 mm outer diameter for all gas handling lines, and valves and fittings made of polyamide. For one experiment the spectrometer including the PTFE filter (0.65 μm pore size) at its inlet line was placed in a climate chamber (CTS C-40/350) to simulate rapid changes in ambient temperature.

2.2. Spectrometer set-up and data evaluation

Absolute spectroscopic amount fraction measurement by CRDS relies on the Beer-Lambert law and the ideal gas law to calculate the amount fraction of the analyte (x) from the measured spectrum and properties of the gas sample. In the simplest case the laser light is scanned across a single absorption line of the analyte, while the absorption coefficient, $\alpha(\bar{\nu})$, is measured as a function of wavenumber. The measured line profile is fitted with a Voigt function to retrieve the integrated absorption coefficient (a). The concentration of the analyte can be calculated according to the following equation:

$$x = \frac{a \cdot k_B \cdot T \cdot K_{\text{gas}}}{S_T \cdot p \cdot r_{\text{iso}}} = \frac{a_{\text{fit}} \cdot K_t \cdot k_B \cdot T \cdot K_{\text{gas}}}{S_0 \cdot K_T \cdot p \cdot r_{\text{iso}}}, \quad (1)$$

where a_{fit} is the measured integrated absorption coefficient with its uncertainty determined from the quality of the fit, and K_t , a correction factor accounting for uncertainty of the wavenumber axis of the spectrometer. p is the pressure and T is the temperature of the gas sample, k_B

Fig. 1. Gas handling set-up for laboratory characterization.

S: spectrometer, P: pump, F: filter, HG: humidity generator, DPM: dew point mirror, NV: needle vale, V: ball valve, 3-V: 3-way valve, MFC: mass flow controller, CC: climate chamber.

is the Boltzmann constant and r_{iso} is a correction factor for the isotopic composition. S_T is the line strength of the probed transition at temperature T , which is known to be temperature-dependent and is calculated from S_0 , the line strength measured at the standard temperature of 296 K, according to the following equation:

$$S_T = S_0 \cdot K_T = S_0 \cdot \frac{Q_{T_0}}{Q_T} \cdot \exp \left[-\frac{h \cdot c \cdot E}{k_B} \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{T_0} \right) \right], \quad (2)$$

where Q is the partition sum [29], h is the Planck constant, c is the speed of light and E is the ground state energy of the transition. We introduced the correction factor K_T for temperature dependence of the line intensity as described by Eq. (2). Furthermore, the correction factor K_{gas} in Eq. (1) accounts for bias caused by the gas handling system, mainly by adsorption-desorption processes and temperature changes in the sampling line altering these processes.

It has been shown in earlier publications by the authors that the above-described method can also be applied when the measured spectrum includes more than one absorption line. As an example, ref [30] describes the application of absolute TDLAS measurements when absorption lines of CO_2 and H_2O are simultaneously recorded on one wavenumber scan. This is an important point considering the complex spectrum of ammonia and interfering atmospheric components (H_2O , CO_2).

Absolute spectroscopic measurement methods aim to achieve traceability of x by ensuring traceability of all input parameters of Eq. (1). In the following sub-sections these parameters are discussed in detail.

Temperature (T). The readings of the temperature sensors in the CRDS spectrometer were compared to the readings of two calibrated temperature sensors (Pt 100, class B). Both sensors are calibrated every 12 months against traceable reference sensors at PTB. Expanded uncertainty ($k = 2$) of the calibration of the sensors was in the range of 0.02 K, while expanded uncertainty of the temperature measurement results is 0.5 K, by far dominated (uncertainty contribution 99.8 %) by the long-term stability of the sensors, as specified by the manufacturer. Both sensors were calibrated approximately 6 months before the measurements shown here. Additionally, directly before comparing the built-in sensors of the Picarro G2103 spectrometer, the agreement between the readings of the two sensors was verified by measuring ambient air

temperature (sensors placed side by side), and was found to be better than 0.02 K.

After this test, the sensors were placed, into the temperature-controlled part of the Picarro G2103 spectrometer, where the cavity is located (“hot box”). One sensor was placed directly on the cavity, and one in the “hot box” further away from the cavity. Three one-day-long measurements were performed, between which the sensors were moved to explore spatial temperature inhomogeneities in the “hot box”. Results of the three measurements are summarized in Table 1. The agreement between readings of the built-in sensor of the spectrometer and the PTB sensors was found to be better than 0.5 K in all cases. The observed differences of 0.14 to 0.44 K can be explained by spatial temperature inhomogeneities in the “hot box”, or bias of the sensor readings. Thus, our measurements show that the accuracy of the built-in sensor is better than 0.5 K. We take 0.5 K as a conservative estimate for expanded uncertainty of the cavity temperature (0.16 % relative expanded uncertainty) and use the readings of 318.15 K of the built-in temperature sensor for our data evaluations.

Pressure (p). The pressure sensor of the CRDS spectrometer was compared to a traceable pressure sensor (Mensor CPT 6100, calibrated against a traceable pressure standard at PTB). The comparison was done by connecting a buffer volume to the instrument’s inlet and letting the pressure in the instrument gas cell and buffer volume equilibrate. The used gas handling system is sketched in Fig. 2. By default, the instrument works with a flow of sample gas. To let the pressure in the gas cell and buffer volume equilibrate, the gas supply was slowly closed using a needle valve. The instrument responds by closing its outlet valve

Table 1

Comparison of the readings of the built-in temperature sensor in the Picarro G2103 spectrometer and two traceable Pt100 temperature sensors placed close to the cavity.

	Measured temperatures		
	Picarro sensor in the cavity / K	PTB sensor on the cavity / K	PTB sensor in the “hot box” / K
1.	318.15	318.29 ± 0.50	318.59 ± 0.50
2.	318.15	318.37 ± 0.50	318.35 ± 0.50
3.	318.15	318.58 ± 0.50	318.44 ± 0.50

Fig. 2. Schematics of the gas handling system for validation of the pressure sensor of the spectrometer.
F: filter, NV: needle valve, V: ball valve, BV: buffer volume, PS: pressure sensor, S: spectrometer, P: pump.

(to the pump) to keep the cell pressure at the setpoint. We waited until a minimum pressure was reached, which was changing only within the digital resolution of the sensor (0.01 hPa) for several minutes. For these intervals, the external sensor (Mensor CPT 6100) and pressure sensor built in the cavity were compared.

The equilibrium pressure which is reached in this way is different from the pressure setpoint. The procedure was thus repeated for three different set points, at 177, 184 and 191 hPa (corresponding to 135 Torr, 140 Torr, and 145 Torr, respectively while the setpoint being 140 Torr during normal measurement) to linearly interpolate the corresponding reading of the external pressure sensor at the exact measurement pressure of the CRDS instrument (Fig. 3). The comparison was repeated 5 times at each pressure setpoint.

As can be seen in Fig. 3, the 186.65 hPa setpoint pressure of the instrument corresponds to a pressure of 185.32 ± 0.21 hPa, as measured by the calibrated pressure sensor. The difference of 1.33 hPa is 0.7 % of the measured pressure and within the range of typical drift of pressure sensors, if regular calibrations are not performed to correct the drift. E.g. the pressure sensor used for the validation showed a drift of approximately 0.7 hPa within 4 years of calibrations compared to the traceable pressure standard. That's why we include the difference in the uncertainty of the pressure readings. We use the value 186.65 hPa with a standard uncertainty of 1.33 hPa (corresponding to 2.66 hPa expanded uncertainty ($k = 2$)) for our evaluations.

Integrated absorption coefficient (a). The wavenumbers, measured by a built-in wavemeter, give the x axis of the measured spectra, while the measured cavity losses (reciprocal of the measured ring-down time times the speed of light) give the y axis of the spectra. Ring-down times are determined from a time-dependent decay of a photodiode signal measured after the cavity. a is determined via a spectral fitting algorithm. To achieve traceability of a , the wavemeter, the photodiode and the time measurement need to be calibrated against traceable standards.

Fig. 3. Pressure values measured by the built-in pressure sensor as a function of pressure measured by a traceable external sensor.

According to technical limitations (these parts of the spectrometer are not accessible for the user) it was not possible to calibrate these parts. Good linearity of InAs and InGaAs photodiodes in the NIR range has been proven in our previous publications [31,32], that's why we consider uncertainty originating from the nonlinearity of the detector negligible compared to other uncertainty sources. Similarly, the uncertainty added by the DAQ card and the decay time measurement are assumed to be negligible compared to other uncertainty components. The correctness of the wavenumber axis can be checked based on the position of spectral lines of NH_3 and H_2O in the measured spectra. Our evaluation shows that there is $<0.5\%$ deviation between the observed line positions and the line positions listed in the HITRAN2020 database. We accounted for this uncertainty via a correction factor K_v , having a value of 1 and expanded relative uncertainty ($k = 2$) of 0.5 %.

As it can be seen in Fig. 4, absorption lines of NH_3 , H_2O and CO_2 are overlapping within the spectral window scanned by the spectrometer, and the spectra are superimposed on a linear background. Although our aim is to determine NH_3 amount fractions, for accurate measurements the absorption lines of H_2O and CO_2 has to be fitted as well, and amount fractions of the other 2 molecules can be calculated from the determined line areas. Based on the HITRAN 2020 database, we identified 8 NH_3 , 8 H_2O and 2 CO_2 lines, to be included in our fitting algorithm. All absorption lines were fitted with a Voigt profile. Relevant line parameters of these lines are listed in Table 2. Complexity of this spectrum, composed of 18 overlapping spectral lines with highly varying intensities requires careful selection of the parameters, which can be fitted as free parameters. We decided to have only four free parameters of the spectral lines in our fitting approach: the line area of a main spectral line for each analyte, which will give the amount fraction of each analyte, and the line position of the strongest NH_3 line. Line areas of the remaining lines are calculated using the ratio of the line intensities (taking into account their temperature dependencies), while positions of the remaining lines are calculated using the differences in the line positions (accounting for their pressure shifts) as given in Table 2. Lorentzian half-widths (w_L) of the spectral lines are calculated using the air and water broadening coefficients (γ_{air} and $\gamma_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$) with their temperature exponents (n_{air} and $n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$) and the cavity pressure (p) and temperature (T), while Gauss half-widths (w_G) are calculated using the cavity temperature, as given by Eqs. (3) and (4):

$$w_L = (1 - x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}) \cdot \gamma_{\text{air}} \cdot p \cdot \left(\frac{T_0}{T}\right)^{n_{\text{air}}} + x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} \cdot \gamma_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} \cdot p \cdot \left(\frac{T_0}{T}\right)^{n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}} \quad (3)$$

$$w_G = \nu_0 \cdot \sqrt{\frac{2 \cdot k_B \cdot T \cdot \ln 2}{m c^2}} \quad (4)$$

where $x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ is the amount fraction of water vapor in the gas sample, ν_0 the wavenumber of the transition, k_B the Boltzmann constant, m the molecular mass, and c the speed of light in vacuum.

We observed a linear background of the spectra, which is instrument-specific, and its intercept and slope are fitted as free parameters. A semi-automatic fitting software has been developed using LabView 2022 and Fityk 1.3.1 [33] to extract the spectra from the spectrometer, perform the spectral fitting and calculate the amount fractions of NH_3 , H_2O and CO_2 using Eq. (1) and (2). The uncertainty component originating for

Fig. 4. Measured data (black squares) and the fitted spectrum (red line) of 100 nmol/mol NH_3 , 20 mmol/mol H_2O and 400 $\mu\text{mol/mol}$ CO_2 in synthetic air. The individual fitted absorption lines are shown with green (NH_3), blue (H_2O) and orange (CO_2), a) in the whole measured spectral window and b) in a smaller window around the NH_3 absorption lines.

Table 2
Fitted spectral lines and used parameters.

Molecule	Line position / cm^{-1}	$U^* (k = 2) / \text{cm}^{-1}$	S_0 HITRAN2020 / cm^{-1}	relative $U^* (S_0) (k = 2)$	S_0 measured [34] / cm^{-1}	relative $U (S_0) (k = 2)$	γ_{air} HITRAN2020 / $\text{cm}^{-1}/\text{atm}$	relative $U^* (\gamma_{\text{air}}) (k = 2)$	$\gamma_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ HITRAN2020 / $\text{cm}^{-1}/\text{atm}$	relative $U^* (\gamma_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}) (k = 2)$	Local quantum numbers	
NH_3	6548.611	0.001	$1.879 \cdot 10^{-21}$	10 %	$1.749 \cdot 10^{-21}$	1 %	0.1017	5 %	0.3306	10 %	4 3 s A2'A2' → 3 2 s E' A2'	
	6548.645	0.01	$3.100 \cdot 10^{-23}$	20 %			0.0946	20 %	0.3481	>20 %	4 3 a	
	6548.798	0.001	$1.847 \cdot 10^{-21}$	10 %	$1.721 \cdot 10^{-21}$	1 %	0.1017	5 %	0.3306	10 %	A2'A2' → 3 2 a E' A2'	
	6548.888	0.01	$1.280 \cdot 10^{-23}$	20 %			0.1003	20 %	0.3481	>20 %	2 0 a	
	6548.925	0.001	$3.561 \cdot 10^{-22}$	10 %	$3.203 \cdot 10^{-22}$	3 %	0.0984	5 %	0.3544	10 %	A1'A2' → 2 1 a E' A2'	
	6549.194	0.01	$3.420 \cdot 10^{-23}$	10 %			0.0963	20 %	0.3481	>20 %		
	6549.287	0.01	$7.200 \cdot 10^{-23}$	10 %			0.0683	20 %	0.3481	>20 %		
	6549.307	0.01	$1.000 \cdot 10^{-23}$	10 %			0.0683	20 %	0.3481	>20 %		
	H_2O	6547.163	0.001	$3.833 \cdot 10^{-24}$	5 %			0.091	5 %	0.371	2 %	6 3 4 → 5 1 5
		6548.489	0.001	$1.859 \cdot 10^{-28}$	20 %			0.0699	20 %	0.298	-	11 4 8 → 10 5 5
6548.578		0.01	$6.423 \cdot 10^{-29}$	>20 %			0.065	20 %	0.208	-	16 5 11 → 15 5 10	
6548.759		0.01	$6.551 \cdot 10^{-29}$	>20 %			0.0314	20 %	0.25	-	13 3 11 → 12 3 10	
6549.125		0.001	$1.588 \cdot 10^{-26}$	5 %			0.025	>20 %	0.281	>20 %	11 0 11 → 10 0 10	
6549.188		0.01	$5.288 \cdot 10^{-27}$	>20 %			0.033	20 %	0.281	20 %	11 1 11 → 10 1 10	
6549.336		0.001	$2.672 \cdot 10^{-26}$	5 %			0.0889	20 %	0.434	5 %	3 3 0 → 2 2 1	
6549.764		0.001	$4.045 \cdot 10^{-24}$	5 %			0.0766	2 %	0.37	10 %	6 4 3 → 5 2 4	
CO_2		6549.107	0.01	$1.218 \cdot 10^{-25}$	5 %			0.074	5 %	0.132	10 %	R16f
		6549.175	0.01	$5.071 \cdot 10^{-27}$	5 %			0.0746	5 %	0.1313	10 %	P16e

* upper limit of the error range given in the HITRAN2020 database interpreted as expanded uncertainty.

the spectral fitting (α_{fit}) is also determined by the applied software. Fit residuals are also plotted in Fig. 4, showing higher noise around strong absorption lines and no clear evidence for etalons in the optical path. Considering the measured spectra and residuals we assume that uncertainty of the fitting is dominated by uncertainty of the measured absorption coefficient, as well as shortcomings of the applied spectral model due to possible line shape issues and uncertainty of spectral line data.

Line intensity (S_T). We measured line intensities of the three strongest NH_3 lines using tunable diode laser absorption spectroscopy and

published the results previously [34]. We observed a 7 % difference between the measured values and the values included in the HITRAN 2020 database. Independent amount fraction measurements with CRDS [35], as well as the measurements presented in this paper demonstrate that our measured line intensities are more accurate. This underlines the fact that accurate line intensities are crucial for absolute spectroscopic amount fraction measurements. However, as shown in Fig. 4 and Table 2, and explained above, we included 15 further absorption lines of NH_3 , H_2O and CO_2 , as well as used further line parameters such as air and water broadening coefficients, together with their temperature

dependence, temperature dependence of the line intensity, and pressure shift of the lines. All these parameters have been taken from the HITRAN 2020 database, which shows that an extensive database with reliable quality control is also inevitable, when spectroscopic measurements are performed in a spectral window with several overlapping absorption lines.

Isotopic composition (r_{iso}). The correction factor for isotopic composition of NH_3 in the gas sample (r_{iso}) is calculated based on natural abundance of the isotopologues published by the IUPAC [36]. We assume that isotopic composition of both the pure NH_3 gas used for our line intensity measurements, as well as the samples used in the experiments presented in this paper fall within the typical natural abundances. Line intensities in the HITRAN database are also published for natural isotopic abundance. Accordingly, r_{iso} has a value of 1 with an expanded uncertainty of 0.1 %, taking into account all possible natural abundances as given in ref [36].

Correction factor for gas handling issues (K_{gas}). Although the gas handling lines, as well as the inlet filter are made of Teflon, a material, which has been found very favorable for NH_3 measurements at low amount fractions [37], sampling issues cannot be neglected. The correction factor K_{gas} has a value of 1, and its uncertainty is determined from the reproducibility of the measurements performed at the same NH_3 amount fractions. For this, different experiments have been considered, which were performed at the same NH_3 and H_2O amount fractions, but on different days and with different measurement histories, i.e. amount fractions measured right before the given experiment. After the measured NH_3 amount fraction has apparently stabilized, one-hour averages of the measured NH_3 amount fraction have been calculated for each experiment and the standard deviation of these results was used as standard uncertainty of the correction factor for gas handling. Although we cannot be sure that this method for calculating uncertainty considers only the uncertainty contribution of the gas handling system, we assume that most uncertainty components in our experiment are systematic, and would affect repeated measurements in the same direction and by the same extent. Uncertainty of the spectral fitting also increases scatter of the measurements results at lower amount fractions, however, this can be efficiently reduced by averaging several spectra, whereas adsorption-desorption processes affect the measurement results on a much longer time scale and will appear in the standard deviation of one-hour averages of data from different measurement series.

Typical uncertainty budget for the calculated amount fractions in two different scenarios are given in Table 3. Zero air containing 50 nmol/mol NH_3 is a typical example for calibrating a monitoring instrument, while ambient air with 11 nmol/mol NH_3 and 15 mmol/mol H_2O amount fraction represents the application in environmental monitoring. As can be seen in the table, the uncertainty budget is not dominated by one component, but several factors have a significant influence. The most important uncertainty contributor in both cases is the gas handling, with 51.4 % relative contribution in case of a dry calibration gas with 50 nmol/mol NH_3 content and 37.7 % in humid

ambient air with 11 nmol/mol NH_3 amount fraction. Spectral fitting, i.e. the integrated absorption coefficient has a minor contribution (4 %) in the calibration gas, however, it becomes the dominant uncertainty component with 54.1 % relative contribution in ambient air, since the NH_3 absorption lines are smaller due to the lower NH_3 amount fraction, and overlapping with much stronger H_2O spectral lines, similarly as shown in Fig. 4. Besides, the pressure and line intensity of the NH_3 lines have a significant contribution to the uncertainty budgets. The overall uncertainty is also significantly different in the two cases, i.e. 2.8 % relative expanded uncertainty ($k = 2$) in dry calibration gas and 6.5 % in ambient air.

2.3. Performed experiments

The spectrometer, the inlet filter and an approximately 3 m long Teflon sampling line with 6 mm outer diameter has been placed in a climate chamber and its sensitivity to environmental temperature has been investigated in the range of 10 to 30 °C.

The Picarro G2103 spectrometer has been known to have a non-negligible offset around 0.6 nmol/mol [15], which might interfere with measurements in the lower nmol/mol range. Therefore, we investigated the zero reading of the instrument in different matrix gases, i.e. nitrogen, synthetic air, as well as purified ambient air with 0–10 mmol/mol H_2O amount fraction.

Response time of the instrument has been determined by preparing mixtures of 50, 100 and 200 nmol/mol NH_3 in synthetic air and using a three-way valve to instantaneously switch between this gas mixture and ammonia-free synthetic air. 10–90 % as well as 1–99 % rise and fall times have been determined for each amount fraction.

Carbon dioxide and water vapor are common components of ambient air and have spectral lines partially overlapping with the ammonia lines, which are probed by this spectrometer, therefore spectral interference is expected. In the case of CO_2 , the spectral interference is expected to be minor, on one hand, due to the better separation of the CO_2 and NH_3 spectral lines and on the other hand due to the relatively small variations in CO_2 amount fractions in ambient air. We investigated the effect of adding 2000 μ mol/mol CO_2 to a gas mixture of 100 nmol/mol NH_3 in purified air. Spectral interference by H_2O is expected to be more significant, as pointed out by Martin et al. [38]. The H_2O spectral lines are stronger and closer to the NH_3 absorption lines, and H_2O amount fraction varies in a much wider range in ambient air. In the case of such high amount fractions, besides overlapping of the lines another effect has to be considered, i.e. pressure broadening of the NH_3 spectral lines by H_2O , as indicated in Eq. (1). We investigated the spectral interference by H_2O in the H_2O amount fraction range of 0–12 mmol/mol at a constant NH_3 amount fraction of approximately 100 nmol/mol.

The measured NH_3 amount fractions have been compared to reference values obtained from a commercial gas cylinder and using calibrated mass flow controllers for preparing test gas mixtures in the nmol/mol amount fraction range. 8 years later the measurements were repeated, using a primary gas mixture prepared at VSL, also equipped

Table 3
Typical uncertainty budget for a single measurement under laboratory conditions in case of two different gas compositions.

Uncertainty component	50 nmol/mol NH_3 in dry zero air			11 nmol/mol NH_3 and 15 mmol/mol H_2O in zero air		
	value	U ($k = 2$)	$U_{rel} / \%$	value	U ($k = 2$)	$U_{rel} / \%$
T	318.15 K	0.5 K	0.3	318.15 K	0.5 K	0.1
p	186.665 hPa	2.66 hPa	26.1	186.638 hPa	2.66 hPa	4.8
S_T	S_0	$1.749 \cdot 10^{-21}$	12.8	$1.749 \cdot 10^{-21}$	$1.749 \cdot 10^{-23}$	2.4
		$cm^{-1}/(molec \cdot cm^{-2})$		$cm^{-1}/(molec \cdot cm^{-2})$	$cm^{-1}/(molec \cdot cm^{-2})$	
	K_T	0.9434	2.1	0.9434	0.0038	0.4
a_{int}	a_{fit}	$3.768 \cdot 10^{-4} cm^{-1}$	4.0	$8.510 \cdot 10^{-5} cm^{-1}$	$4.08 \cdot 10^{-6} cm^{-1}$	54.1
	K_v	1	3.2	1	0.005	0.6
r_{iso}		1	0.1	1	0.001	0.0
K_{gas}		1	51.4	1	0.04	37.7
x_{NH_3}		50.01 nmol/mol		11.29 nmol/mol	0.74 nmol/mol	

with a calibrated dilution system using MFCs to prepare reference gas mixtures with traceable NH_3 amount fraction in the nmol/mol range. For H_2O a calibrated dew-point mirror has been used as a reference in the range of 0–12 mmol/mol. Since the CO_2 absorption line is very weak and covered by a stronger H_2O line, although the spectrometer can give a rough estimation, it is not suitable for accurately determining the CO_2 amount fraction in the measured gas mixture.

3. Results

As shown in Fig. 5b, experiments in the climate chamber revealed an excellent stability of the NH_3 amount fraction readings even in case of a temperature step from 10 to 30 °C within 20 min. This indicates that neither the spectrometer itself, nor the Teflon inlet filter or sampling line is sensitive to usual changes in ambient temperature. However, we emphasize the importance of material choice in case of the sampling line. Fig. 5a shows the same experiment using the same Teflon inlet filter and sampling line, including an additional approximately 5 cm long rubber tube (material unknown) for connecting the filter to the inlet of the spectrometer. In this case, a temporal increase by approximately 5 % of the measured NH_3 amount fraction has been observed, when the ambient temperature changed from 10 °C to 30 °C. Although it is a rather minor effect, it might be of importance in high-precision measurements in environments with varying temperature and can easily be eliminated by using appropriate materials (e.g. Teflon) for the entire gas handling system.

Fig. 6a shows the zero readings of the spectrometer. The red curve indicates the readings when using the Picarro G2103 spectrometer as a regular user. In this case we observed a zero offset of 0.62 nmol/mol, which agrees well with values reported previously in literature. However, the zero reading of our optical gas standard for the same set of measurements is significantly lower, 0.12 nmol/mol. Fig. 6b shows the average zero reading of the spectrometer in different matrix gases. The offset was found to increase with increasing humidity, as shown by the trend line in Fig. 6b. The largest offset measured at 10 mmol/mol H_2O amount fraction was around 0.28 nmol/mol compared to 0.12 and 0.15 nmol/mol measured in dry nitrogen and zero air. Since the observed difference is smaller than its uncertainty, and our experimental set-up didn't allow measurements above 10 mmol/mol humidity, we cannot accurately quantify the effect of humidity on the observed offset. Based on the results shown in Fig. 6b an offset around 0.4–0.5 nmol/mol can be predicted for a humidity of 27 mmol/mol H_2O amount fraction corresponding to 100 % relative humidity at 30 °C, which can be considered the most humid condition in typical field applications. This offset might be significant when measuring very low (0–10 nmol/mol) NH_3 amount fractions under such humid conditions, however we expect that for most practical applications the zero offset of our spectrometer can be considered negligible.

Fig. 7 shows spectra measured in synthetic air after different purging times. The symbols in the figure represent the measured absorption coefficient (averaged for 40 measured spectra) after subtracting the

linear background determined during the spectral fitting, while the lines show the fitted spectra. As confirmed also by the fit residuals plotted in Fig. 7b, the measured and simulated spectra agree well, proving that our spectral evaluation works well even at such low amount fractions, and the higher values given by the spectrometer are most probably a data evaluation artefact of the built-in algorithm. Table 4 shows the NH_3 amount fraction values given by the Picarro G2103 spectrometer and the results of our spectral evaluation, for the data shown in Fig. 7. A remaining NH_3 amount fraction of 1 nmol/mol was observed after 1 h purging with synthetic air, while after 3 h we still measured 0.5 nmol/mol. The true zero value was only reached after at least one-day purging, which is important to keep in mind for calibration of analyzers, both for the zero point and any calibration points for lower amount fractions, i.e., in the 0–50 nmol/mol range. Too short purging times will result in considerably higher uncertainty and biased results. The remaining offset of 0.12 nmol/mol with our spectral evaluation is either an artefact of our spectral fitting, or remaining NH_3 in our zero gas. We didn't investigate this further, since the measured offset is a factor of 2 lower than its uncertainty and thus negligible.

Response time of the spectrometer has been determined from the data shown in Fig. 8, measured in dry gas mixtures, at a laboratory temperature of 297–299 K, using an approximately 3 m long Teflon inlet line. For comparability, we show the relative NH_3 amount fraction on the y-axis, 0 % referring to the average zero reading, and 100 % referring to the average NH_3 amount fraction, after the readings have stabilized at the 50, 100 or 200 nmol/mol level. Table 5 summarizes the measured response times. Fall times have been found to be shorter than rise times by a factor up to 2.5, and it has been observed that the stabilization time is longer at lower amount fractions. 10–90 % response time was found to be shorter than 2 min in each case, while 1–99 % response time was in the range of several minutes, up to half an hour for the steps studied in this work. This is sufficient for typical laboratory calibrations, however we note that the response time of our spectrometer is expected to be longer at NH_3 amount fractions below 50 nmol/mol. Also, the response time of the instrument to be calibrated has to be taken into account, which might result in certain calibration steps needing more time (several hours).

A step change from 2000 $\mu\text{mol/mol}$ to 0 $\mu\text{mol/mol}$ CO_2 , while keeping the NH_3 amount fraction constant at approximately 100 nmol/mol resulted in an apparent increase of only 0.4 nmol/mol in the measured NH_3 amount fraction (Fig. 9). In outdoor air, the natural fluctuations of CO_2 amount fraction around the average 400 $\mu\text{mol/mol}$ are much smaller, well below 100 $\mu\text{mol/mol}$. Even in indoor air a CO_2 amount fraction of 2000 $\mu\text{mol/mol}$ is considered high, typical CO_2 levels in sufficiently ventilated indoor spaces are 400–1000 $\mu\text{mol/mol}$. Under these circumstances the cross-sensitivity of our optical gas standard to CO_2 is negligible, our spectral evaluation algorithm models the measured spectrum accurately and successfully eliminates cross-sensitivity caused by overlapping spectral lines.

Spectral interference caused by H_2O was found to be much more significant. Similarly, as in the case of CO_2 , cross-sensitivity caused by

Fig. 5. Measured ammonia amount fractions during a step change in the air temperature from 10 to 30 °C, a) with Teflon sampling lines containing a 5 cm long rubber tube at the inlet and b) with Teflon sampling line without any other material.

Fig. 6. a) NH₃ amount fractions measured in zero air, red symbols: readings of the Picarro instrument, black symbols: results of our spectral evaluation b) NH₃ amount fractions measured in different zero gases using PTB's spectral evaluation: dry nitrogen, dry zero air, as well as zero air with 0.25 %–1 % absolute humidity, bars indicate expanded uncertainty ($k = 2$) of the results.

Fig. 7. Spectra measured in synthetic air after different purging time.

Table 4

NH₃ amount fraction readings of the Picarro G2103 instrument and results determined by PTB's spectral evaluation in synthetic air, after different purging times.

Purging time	x_{NH_3} (Picarro G2103) / nmol/mol	x_{NH_3} (PTB's evaluation) /nmol/mol
>2 days	0.89	0.12
3 h	1.27	0.50
1 h	1.78	1.01

overlapping spectral lines can be efficiently eliminated by our spectral evaluation method. However, due to the high H₂O amount fractions (in the mmol/mol range) expected in ambient air, H₂O also affects the line width of the spectral lines. Fig. 10a shows a 3-day long measurement series, where the NH₃ amount fraction was kept constant around 95 nmol/mol, and the H₂O amount fraction is varied between 2.5 mmol/mol and 10 mmol/mol. Variations in the NH₃ amount fractions are caused by variations in laboratory temperature. This experiment has been carried out in a laboratory, where air temperature varied between 294 K –297 K during the measurement time shown in Fig. 10a, and these temperature changes affected adsorption of NH₃ on the surface of the pressure reducer (stainless steel, without any special surface

treatment or coating), thus causing up to 2 nmol/mol variations in the measured NH₃ amount fractions. Despite these slower, temperature-induced variations, step changes in the measured NH₃ amount fractions can be clearly observed every time when the H₂O amount fraction has been changed and the pressure broadening by H₂O has not been taken into account (black curve). However, as the green curve shows, this spectral interference can be eliminated by including the pressure broadening caused by H₂O. Fig. 10b shows the measured NH₃ amount fractions (relative to the average 95 nmol/mol) as a function of H₂O amount fractions for periods, where the NH₃ amount fraction was stable. The slope of the fitted line is smaller than its uncertainty if we include pressure broadening by H₂O, while it agrees well with the value reported previously by Martin et al. [38], when this effect is not taken into account. We note that since 2016 the water correction developed by Martin et al. [38] has been included in all Picarro G2103 instruments, for practical reasons as an empirical correction. Our results provide a quantitative determination of the H₂O broadening effect and show that it can also be corrected by an improved spectral fitting algorithm.

Finally, linearity of the measured amount fractions was investigated, and the amount fractions measured by our spectrometer were compared to traceable standards. Fig. 11 shows the measurement results for NH₃. First, reference gas mixtures were prepared using a commercial gas mixture (10 $\mu\text{mol/mol}$ NH₃ in synthetic air, from Linde), which was diluted with zero air using MFCs calibrated against a traceable flow meter. We found very good linearity, agreement between the calculated and measured amount fractions, as well as a negligible offset (i.e., smaller than its uncertainty), as shown in Fig. 11a. Eight years later we had the opportunity to perform measurements with our spectrometer on gas mixtures produced using a traceable reference cylinder (10 $\mu\text{mol/mol}$ NH₃ in nitrogen) and a two-step dilution system consisting of calibrated MFCs, provided by VSL, the Dutch metrology institute. Again, very good linearity and excellent agreement between the calculated and measured amount fractions have been observed, as well as a negligible offset (i.e., smaller than its uncertainty), as shown in Fig. 11b This comparison was part of a larger laboratory inter-comparison of NH₃ gas standards, where our spectrometer was also compared to three different dynamic reference gas generators in the 0–400 nmol/mol amount fraction range, both in dry gas mixtures and in gas mixtures with 15 mmol/mol humidity content. The results of this inter-comparison campaign will be published elsewhere.

As shown in Table 2, the H₂O amount spectral lines are considerably weaker than the NH₃ lines, the strongest H₂O line visible in the spectral window of the instrument being almost 5 orders of magnitude weaker than the NH₃ lines. For such weak lines it is very difficult to obtain accurate line data. Line intensities of the H₂O lines listed in Table 2 are calculated values [39] with uncertainties >20 % for many lines. Results

Fig. 8. Measured relative ammonia amount fraction as a function of time, after a step change of the ammonia amount fraction. For better orientation, the blue line corresponds to 10 % and 90 % relative ammonia amount fraction in Figure a) and b), and 1 % and 99 % in c) and d), respectively.

Table 5

Response time of the instrument in dry gas mixtures.

	0-200 nmol/ mol	0-100 nmol/ mol	0-50 nmol/ mol	200-0 nmol/ mol	100-0 nmol/ mol	50-0 nmol/ mol
10-90 %	54 s	92 s	103 s	35 s	37 s	58 s
1-99 %	23 min	29 min	25 min	9 min	15 min	26 min

however, the amount fractions measured by our instrument are 14 % higher than the reference values. The deviation is most probably due to inaccurate H₂O line intensities, and although this is within the given uncertainty of the used line intensities, it indicates that more accurate line intensities are required for accurate H₂O amount fraction measurements. However, using this calibration curve, the instrument is capable of accurate determination of H₂O amount fraction as well, and the measured H₂O amount fractions are used for accurately calculating the line widths of the spectral lines, considering foreign broadening caused by H₂O.

4. Conclusions and outlook

Based on the presented results we conclude that our spectrometer has the potential to become an optical gas standard, and thereby a useful tool for calibrating and validating other instruments used for environmental ammonia monitoring. Our spectrometer has been proven to operate accurately in the 0-400 nmol/mol range, with excellent linearity and negligible offset. Cross-sensitivity to CO₂ is negligible, and the minor cross-sensitivity for H₂O could be successfully eliminated by applying an advanced spectral data evaluation algorithm. The 1-99 % response time of the spectrometer is less than half an hour for step changes from at least 50 nmol/mol to zero and vice versa, which makes it suitable for laboratory calibrations with gas mixtures. However, it has to be noted that overnight purging is necessary to reach a true zero point, and response time at much lower amount fractions has to be further investigated. Measurements performed 8 years apart show excellent stability of the spectrometer. However, since we only had one opportunity to compare our spectrometer to a traceable, reference material based gas standard so far, its long-term stability has to be confirmed by further regular comparison to traceable standards.

The presented results prove the applicability of our spectrometer in a laboratory environment for the calibration of field instrumentation, newly developed instruments, or certification of gas mixtures. The

Fig. 9. NH₃ amount fractions measured during a step change of CO₂ amount fraction from 2000 µmol/mol to 0 µmol/mol.

of a comparison of the H₂O amount fractions measured by our spectrometer to amount fractions measured by a traceable dew point mirror are shown in Fig. 12. Good linearity and negligible offset were observed;

Fig. 10. NH₃ amount fractions with the foreign broadening by H₂O taken into account (green curve) and not taken into account (black curve), in a gas sample with H₂O amount fraction varying between 2.5 and 10 mmol/mol b) NH₃ amount fraction measured by the spectrometer as a function of H₂O amount fraction with the foreign broadening by H₂O taken into account (red symbols) and not taken into account (black symbols).

Fig. 11. Comparison of the NH₃ amount fraction results measured by our spectrometer to reference NH₃ amount fractions given by gas standards from cylinders a) in 2016 using a commercial gas mixture from Linde and b) in 2024 using a traceable primary gas mixture prepared by VSL.

Fig. 12. Comparison of the measured H₂O amount fraction results to PTB's traceable humidity standard.

spectrometer is not sensitive to changes in environmental temperature, which enables on-site calibrations in field settings with gas mixtures, but using the NH₃ amount fractions measured by our spectrometer as a reference value. In this case, the requirements for the used gas mixtures and the dilution system are much lower than in the case of calibrations using reference gas mixtures alone, without a reference spectrometer. However, we note that a considerable amount of further research is needed to enable side-by-side calibration or validation of field instrumentation using ambient air. Our current work included measurements in aerosol-free gas mixtures, ensuring that the sampling line and filters of our spectrometer remain clean.

Our spectrometer has participated in a laboratory comparison of NH₃ gas standards. Part of the results of this comparison are shown in Fig. 11b Besides the traceable gas cylinder equipped with the dilution system, and our spectrometer, three newly developed dynamic NH₃ dynamic reference gas generators participated in this comparison, and the measurements were performed in dry gas mixtures, as well as in gas mixtures with approximately 15 mmol/mol water vapor. The results of this experiment will be published separately. Further such comparisons to standards will promote the applicability of our spectrometer as an optical gas standard.

First calibrations of commercial instruments using our spectrometer have already been performed, and further measurements are planned. The collected data will enable evaluation of the applicability of our spectrometer in different laboratory calibration exercises. Field applicability of our spectrometer has been demonstrated in 2016 [18], where

the instrument measured NH₃ amount fractions in a mobile laboratory in the 0–300 nmol/mol range for 10 days on a grazed grassland before and after fertilization. In this field campaign we investigated the applicability of our spectrometer as a reference instrument under field conditions. Although the results are promising, we emphasize that it was only one short measurement campaign, it needs further work to evaluate field applicability of our spectrometer as a reference instrument. Regular sampling of aerosol-loaded ambient air with rapidly changing NH₃ and H₂O amount fractions will primarily affect uncertainty originating from gas sampling, and changing intervals of the sampling lines and filters, as well as the effect of the spectrometer's relatively long response time on the measurement results have to be thoroughly evaluated.

We consider our instrument a good candidate for an optical gas standard for calibration tasks performed with gas mixtures, which can offer a competitive alternative to high-accuracy reference material-based gas standards such as cylinders combined with dilution systems or newly developed dynamic reference gas generators, thereby further expanding the toolkit for NH₃ amount fraction calibrations for environmental monitoring. To become a regular standard, a CMC claim has to be submitted, and reliable operation of the instrument has to be proven over a longer time, e.g., by regular participation in key comparisons.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Andrea Pogány: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Nils O. B. Lüttschwager:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Software, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Gourab Dutta Banik:** Writing – original draft, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Stefan Persijn:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Ewoud J.J. de Boed:** Writing – original draft, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Christophe Sutour:** Writing – original draft, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Tatiana Macé:** Writing – original draft, Conceptualization. **Javis A. Nwaboh:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Resources, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Olav Werhahn:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Volker Ebert:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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